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Some New Classes of Antimagic Trees

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Abstract:

This paper presents some newly designed Trees namely Arrow, Thorn and Bush and the Antimagic labellings discovered for these Trees. Algorithms, theorems and formulas of Antimagic labelling for all these three classes of Trees are being presented.

Keywords: Antimagic labelling, Tree, Arrow Tree, Thorn Tree, Bush Tree.

1. Introduction:

A Tree is a graph defined as *connected* and *acyclic*. Tree is a widely studied class of graphs with a broad range of applications. Several kinds of Trees exist and depending on the structure of a particular kind of Tree, applications can be discovered.

Algorithms for Antimagic Bipartite Trees have been given in [1] along with

[17]

algorithms for other kinds of graph labellings also such as *graceful*, *harmonious*, *sequential* and *felicitous*. [2] gives Antimagic labellings and also other kinds of labellings for Paths (a kind of Tree) using *lexicographic order* (an order in which 1234 is *permutation 1* appearing before 1243 which is *permutation 2* in the 4! permutations of 1, 2, 3, 4 as in a lexicon/dictionary). In [3], graphs related in structure to Paths are presented for Antimagic labelling. [4] presents Trees with several degree 2 vertices with restriction on the subgraph induced by the degree 2 vertices and its complement. Antimagic labelling of various classes of graphs including Paths are given with new algorithms for variations of Antimagic labelling in [5]. Applications of various labelled graphs including Antimagic Trees have been presented in [6]. A k -Antimagic labelling for Caterpillars (a kind of Tree) is given in [7]. [8] presents the Antimagic labellings of two recursive classes of Trees called Binomial Tree and Fibonacci Tree.

Section 2 presents the main results i.e. the algorithms, theorems and formulas (for the *induced vertex labels*) for all the 3 newly designed classes of Trees namely Arrow, Thorn and Bush Trees in the respective subsections 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3. Conclusion is presented in the section 3.

2. Main Results:

A *graph labelling* is an assignment of numbers (labels) to vertices (edges) such that the *induced* edge (vertex) labels follow certain pattern. The operations employed for finding the induced vertex/edge labels may be addition, subtraction, etc.

Antimagic Labelling: It is an *edge labelling* scheme such that the induced vertex label for each vertex formed by addition of all the labels of the incident edges on a vertex is distinct for each vertex. In a graph $G(p, q)$ with p vertices and q edges, the edges are numbered (labelled) with 1, 2, 3, ..., q .

2.1 Arrow Trees:

Arrow ($A_{m,n,k}$) is a new kind of Tree where m : number of layer(s) on each side of the Central Line termed as Upper Layer(s) and Lower Layer(s). The Upper (Lower) Layer of edges farthest from the Central Line is Upper (Lower) Layer 1, the next closer layer to the Central Line is Upper (Lower) Layer 2, ..., Upper (Lower)

Layer m namely $UL_m(LL_m)$; n is the number of vertices on each Layer; $k = n + 1$ is the number of vertices on Central Line. **Figure 1** shows Arrow $(A_{1,4,5})$, where $m=1, n=4$ and $k=5$.

Description and Naming of the Vertices and Edges for Arrow Trees $(A_{1,n,k}) \Rightarrow T(p+1, p) // p+1$ vertices, p edges; $p=3n, k=n+1 //$

Vertices:

- Pendant vertices of Upper Layer (UL_1); $u_j: j=1$ to n (left to right)
- Pendant vertices of Lower Layer (LL_1); $u_{n+j}: j=1$ to n (right to left)
- Vertices on the Central Line; $v_k: k=1$ to $n+1$ (left to right)

Edges:

for $j=1$ to n

- Edges of UL_1 : $e_j = (u_j, v_{j+1})$ (left to right)
- Edges of LL_1 : $e_{n+j} = (u_{n+j}, v_{n-j+2})$ (right to left)
- Edges on Central Line are: $e_{2n+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1})$ (left to right)

End for

Figure 1: Arrow $(A_{1,4,5})$ or Tree $(T(13, 12))$; 13 vertices, 12 edges)

Illustration: *Arrow Tree* $(A_{1,4,5}) \Rightarrow T(13,12)$, // $n = 4, p = 12$ //

For $j = 1$ to n i.e., for $j = 1$ to 4.

Upper Layer (UL_1) edges $e_j = (u_j, v_{j+1})$ labeled with j i.e., 1, 2, 3, 4 // left to right //

Lower Layer (LL_1) edges $e_{n+j} = (u_{n+j}, v_{n-j+2})$ labeled with $n+j$ i.e., 5, 6, 7, 8 // right to left //

Central Line edges $e_{2n+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1})$ labeled with $(p-n+1$ to $p)$: $p-n+1 = 9$ to $p = 12$ i.e., 9, 10, 11, 12 // left to right //

Induced vertex labels:

Upper Layer (UL_1) pendant vertices u_j with j i.e., 1, 2, 3, 4 // left to right //

Lower Layer (LL_1) pendant vertices u_{n+j} with $n+j$ i.e., 5, 6, 7, 8 // right to left //

Central Line: leftmost vertex v_1 : $2n + 1 = 9$, intermediate 3 vertices for $j = 2$ to 3 i.e. v_2, v_3, v_4 : $6n + 2j = 28, 30, 32$; rightmost vertex v_5 : $5n + 1 = 21$.

Algorithm for Arrow $(A_{1,n,k})$:

// $p+1$ vertices, p edges; $p = 3n, k = n+1$ //

Begin

for $j = 1$ to n

 Label the edges of Upper Layer (UL_1) with j from left to right

 // There are n edges in each Layer //

end for

for $j = (n + 1)$ to $2n$

 Label the edges of Lower Layer (LL_1) with j from right to left

end for

for $j = (p - n + 1)$ to p

 Label Central Line edges with j from left to right // n edges //

end for

End.

Theorem: Arrow Trees $(A_{1,n,k})$ are Antimagic.

Proof: For $j = 1$ to n let Edges of UL_1 : $e_j = (u_j, v_{j+1})$ (left to right)

Edges of LL_1 : $e_{n+j} = (u_{n+j}, v_{n-j+2})$ (right to left)

Edges on Central Line are: $e_{2n+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1})$ (left to right)

The Edge Labels are as follows:

$$f(u_j, v_{j+1}) = j // \text{ up to } n, \text{ left to right on } UL_1 //$$

$$f(u_{n+j}, v_{n-j+2}) = n+j // \text{ from } (n+1) \text{ to } 2n, \text{ right to left on } LL_1 //$$

$$f(v_j, v_{j+1}) = 2n+j // \text{ Central Line, left to right } //$$

The induced Vertex Labels are as follows:

$$f^*(u_j) = j // \text{ Pendant vertices of } UL_1 //$$

$$f^*(u_{n+j}) = n+j // \text{ Pendant vertices of } LL_1 //$$

// Pendant vertex labels are consecutive integers //

$$f^*(v_1) = 2n+1 \text{ or } p-n+1 // \text{ leftmost vertex on Central Line } //$$

$$f^*(v_j) = 6n+2j; j=2 \text{ to } n // \text{ intermediate vertices on Central Line } //$$

$$f^*(v_{n+1}) = 5n+1 // \text{ right most vertex on Central Line } //$$

// Central line vertices make an arithmetic progression with common difference 2 except leftmost and rightmost vertices //

Since all the induced vertex labels are distinct therefore, the Arrow trees $(A_{1,n,k})$ are Antimagic.

Results:

Upper and Lower layer vertex are labelled with common difference 1, Central line vertex are labelled with common difference 2 except Left and Right most vertex, Left most vertex of central line is labelled with $p-n+1$ or $2n+1$, Right most vertex of central line is labelled with $3p-4n+1$ or $5n+1$.

Algorithm and theorem for the Antimagic labelling for the generalized Arrow Trees Arrow $(A_{m,n,k})$ are as follows:

Description and Naming of the Vertices and Edges:

Vertices:

Pendant vertices of Upper Layer (UL_1); $u_j: j = 1$ to n (left to right)

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Pendant vertices of Lower Layer (LL_1); u_{n+j} : $j = 1$ to n (right to left)

Intermediate vertices of UL_i & UL_{i+1} above the Central Line: UL_{2in+j} ; $i = 1$ to $m-1$, $j = 1$ to n (left to right)

Intermediate vertices of LL_i & LL_{i+1} below the Central Line: $u_{(2i+1)n+j}$; $i = 1$ to $m-1$, $j = 1$ to n (right to left)

Vertices on the Central Line; v_k : $k = 1$ to $n+1$ (left to right)

Edges:

For $i=1$ to $m-1$, $j=1$ to n

Edges of UL_i : $e_{2(i-1)n+j} = (u_{2(i-1)n+j}, u_{2in+j})$ (left to right)

Edges of LL_i : $e_{(2i-1)n+j} = (u_{(2i-1)n+j}, u_{(2i+1)n+j})$ (right to left)

Edges of UL_m : $e_{2(m-1)n+j} = (u_{2(m-1)n+j}, v_{j+1})$ (left to right)

Edges of LL_m : $e_{(2m-1)n+j} = (u_{(2m-1)n+j}, v_{n-j+2})$ (right to left)

Edges on Central Line are: $e_{2mn+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1})$ (left to right)

Algorithm for Generalized Arrow Trees: Arrow Trees $(A_{m,n,k}) \Rightarrow Tree T(p+1, p)$

with $p+1$ vertices and p edges // $p=(2m+1)n$, $k = n+1$ //

Begin

For $i=1$ to m

For $j=2(i-1)n+1$ to $(2i-1)n$

Label edges of UL_i with j from left to right

// There are n edges in each Layer //

end for

end for

For $i=1$ to m

For $j=((2i-1)n+1)$ to $2in$

Label edges of LL_i with j from right to left

end for

end for

For $j = p - n + 1$ to p

Label Central Line edges with j from left to right // n edges //

end for

End.

Theorem: Arrow Trees $(A_{m,n,k})$ are Antimagic.

Proof: For $i=1$ to $m-1$, $j=1$ to n

Let Edges of UL_i : $e_{2(i-1)n+j} = (u_{2(i-1)n+j}, u_{2in+j})$ (left to right)

Edges of LL_i : $e_{(2i-1)n+j} = (u_{(2i-1)n+j}, u_{(2i+1)n+j})$ (right to left)

Edges of UL_m : $e_{2(m-1)n+j} = (u_{2(m-1)n+j}, v_{j+1})$ (left to right)

Edges of LL_m : $e_{(2m-1)n+j} = (u_{(2m-1)n+j}, v_{n-j+2})$ (right to left)

Edges on Central Line are: $e_{2mn+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1})$ (left to right)

The Edge Labels are as follows:

$$f(u_{2(i-1)n+j}, u_{2in+j}) = 2(i-1)n+j \quad (1)$$

// from $(2(i-1)n+1)$ to $(2i-1)n$, left to right on UL_i //

$$f(u_{(2i-1)n+j}, u_{(2i+1)n+j}) = (2i-1)n+j \quad (2)$$

// from $((2i-1)n+1)$ to $2in$, right to left on LL_i //

$$f(u_{2(m-1)n+j}, v_{j+1}) = 2(m-1)n+j \quad (3)$$

// from $(2(m-1)n+1)$ to $(2m-1)n$, left to right on UL_m //

$$f(u_{(2m-1)n+j}, v_{n-j+2}) = (2m-1)n+j \quad (4)$$

// from $((2m-1)n+1)$ to $2mn$, right to left on LL_m //

$$f(v_j, v_{j+1}) = 2mn+j \quad \text{// Central Line, left to right //} \quad (5)$$

The induced Vertex Labels are as follows:

$$f^*(u_j) = j \quad \text{// Pendant vertices of } UL_1 \quad \text{//} \quad (6)$$

$$f^*(u_{n+j}) = n+j \quad \text{// Pendant vertices of } LL_1 \quad \text{//} \quad (7)$$

// Pendant vertex labels are consecutive integers //

$$f^*(u_{2in+j}) = 2[(2i-1)n+j] \quad (8)$$

// Intermediate vertices of UL_i & UL_{i+1} above the Central Line //

$$f^*(u_{(2i+1)n+j}) = 2(2in+j) \quad (9)$$

// Intermediate vertices of LL_i & LL_{i+1} below the Central Line //

// Middle vertex labels make an *arithmetic progression* with common

difference 2 //

$$f^*(v_1) = 2mn+1 \quad \text{// leftmost vertex on the Central Line //} \quad (10)$$

$$f^*(v_j) = 2[(4m-1)n+j] ; j=2 \text{ to } n \quad \text{// intermediate vertices on the Central}$$

Line //

$$(11)$$

$$f^*(v_{n+1}) = (6m - 1)n + 1 \text{ // right most vertex on the Central Line // } \quad (12)$$

// Central line vertex labels make an *arithmetic progression* with common difference 2 except leftmost and rightmost vertices //

Since all the induced vertex labels are distinct. Therefore, the Arrow trees $(A_{m,n,k})$ are Antimagic.

Results:

Pendant vertex of Upper and Lower layer are labelled with common difference 1, Middle vertex of Upper & Lower layer and Central line vertex are labelled with common difference 2 except Left and Right most vertex of Central line, Left most vertex of central line is labelled with $p - n + 1$ or $2mn + 1$, Right most vertex of central line is labelled with $3p - 4n + 1$ or $(6m - 1)n + 1$.

Illustration:

Arrow Tree $(A_{3,5,6}) \Rightarrow T(36, 35)$, // $m = 3, n = 5, p = 12, k = 6$ //

For $i = 1$ to $m - 1, j = 1$ to n i.e., for $i = 1$ to $2j = 1$ to 5

Upper Layer (UL_1) edges $e_j = (u_j, u_{2n+j})$ labeled with j i.e., 1,2,3,4, 5 // left to right by (1) //

Lower Layer (LL_1) edges $e_{n+j} = (u_{n+j}, u_{3n+j})$ labeled with $n + j$ i.e., 6,7,8, 9,10 // right to left by (2) //

Upper Layer (UL_2) edges $e_{2n+j} = (u_{2n+j}, u_{4n+j})$ labeled with $2n + j$ i.e., 11,12,13,14,15 // left to right by (1) //

Lower Layer (LL_2) edges $e_{3n+j} = (u_{3n+j}, u_{5n+j})$ labeled with $3n + j$ i.e., 16,17,18, 19,20 // right to left by (2) //

Upper Layer (UL_3) edges $e_{4n+j} = (u_{4n+j}, v_{j+1})$ labeled with $4n + j$ i.e., 21,22,23,24,25 // left to right by (3) //

Lower Layer (LL_3) edges $e_{5n+j} = (u_{5n+j}, v_{n-j+2})$ labeled with $5n + j$ i.e.,26,27,28, 29, 30 // right to left by (4) //

Central Line edges $e_{6n+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1})$ labeled with $(p - n + 1$ to $p)$ or $2mn + j$: (left to right)

$p - n + 1 = 31$ to $p = 35$ i.e., 31,32,33,34,35 by (5)

Induced vertex labels:

Upper Layer (UL_1) pendant vertices u_j with j i.e., 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 // left to right by (6) //
 Lower Layer (LL_1) pendant vertices u_{n+j} with $n + j$ i.e., 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 // right to left by (7) //
 Intermediate vertices u_{2n+j} of UL_1 & UL_2 with $2(n + j)$ i.e., 12, 14, 16, 18, 20 // left to right by (8) //
 Intermediate vertices u_{3n+j} of LL_1 & LL_2 with $2(2n + j)$ i.e., 22, 24, 26, 28, 30 //left to right by (9) //
 Intermediate vertices u_{4n+j} of UL_2 & UL_3 with $2(3n + j)$ i.e., 32, 34, 36, 38, 40 // left to right by (8) //
 Intermediate vertices u_{5n+j} of LL_2 & LL_3 with $2(4n + j)$ i.e., 42, 44, 46, 48, 50 //left to right by (9) //
 Central Line: leftmost vertex v_1 : $2mn + 1 = 31$, intermediate 4 vertices for $j = 2$ to 5 i.e. v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5 : $2[(4m - 1)n + j] = 114, 116, 118, 120$; rightmost vertex v_6 : $(6m - 1)n + 1 = 86$. by (10), (11) & (12).

Figure 2: Arrow ($A_{3,5,6}$) or Tree ($T(36, 35)$); 36 vertices, 35 edges)

2.2 Thorn Trees:

Thorn (m, n, k) is a new kind of Tree where m : Total number of vertices on each Layer on both sides of the Central Line termed as Upper Layer(s) and Lower Layer(s). The Upper (Lower) Layer of edges farthest from the Central Line is Upper (Lower) Layer 1, the next closer layer to the Central Line is Upper (Lower) Layer 2, ..., Upper (Lower) Layer m namely $UL_m(LL_m)$ n : number of Layers on each side of the Central Line, k : Total number of vertices on the Central Line.

Description and Naming of the Vertices and Edges for Thorn Trees $(m, 1, k) \Rightarrow T(p + 1, p)$ // $p + 1$ vertices, p edges; $p = 2m, k = m + 1$ //

Vertices:

- Pendant vertices of Upper Layer (UL); $u_{2j-1}; j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)
- Pendant vertices of Lower Layer (LL); $u_{2j}; j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)
- Vertices on the Central Line (CL); $v_j; j = 1$ to $m + 1$ (left to right)

Edges:

- Edges of Upper Layer (UL); $e_{2j-1} = (u_{2j-1}, v_{2j}) : j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)
- Edges of Lower Layer (LL); $e_{2j} = (u_{2j}, v_{2j+1}) : j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)
- Edges on Central Line (CL) are: $e_{m+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1}) : j = 1$ to m (left to right)

Figure 3: Thorn Tree $(4, 1, 5)$ or Tree $(T(9, 8))$; 9 vertices, 8 edges

Illustration: Thorn Tree $(4,1,5) \Rightarrow T(9,8)$, // $m = 4, k = 5, p = 8$ //

For $j = 1$ to $m/2$ i.e., for $j = 1$ to 2

Upper Layer edges $e_{2j-1} = (u_{2j-1}, v_{2j})$ labeled with $2j - 1$ i.e., 1, 3 // left to right //

Lower Layer edges $e_{2j} = (u_{2j}, v_{2j+1})$ labeled with $2j$ i.e., 2, 4 // left to right //

Central Line edges $e_{2m+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1})$ labeled with $(p$ to $p - m + 1)$: $p = 8$ to $p - m + 1 = 15$ i.e., 8, 7, 6, 5 // left to

right, step -1 //

Induced vertex labels:

Upper Layer pendant vertices u_{2j-1} with $2j - 1$ i.e., 1, 3 // left to right //

Lower Layer pendant vertices u_{2j} with $2j$ i.e., 2, 4 // left to right //

Central Line: leftmost vertex v_1 : $2m = 8$, intermediate 3 vertices v_j for $j = 2$ to 4 i.e. v_2, v_3, v_4 : $4m - j + 2 = 16, 15, 14$; rightmost vertex v_5 : $p + 1$ or $2m + 1 = 9$.

Algorithm for Thorn $(m, 1, k)$:

// $p + 1$ vertices, p edges; $p = 2m, k = m + 1$ //

Begin

for $j = 1$ to $m/2$

Label the edges of Upper Layer with $2j - 1$ from left to right

// There are 2 edges in each Layer //

end for

for $j = 1$ to $m/2$

Label the edges of Lower Layer with $2j$ from left to right

end for

for $j = p$ to $(p - m + 1)$ // step -1 //

Label Central Line edges with j from left to right // m edges //

end for

End.

Theorem: Thorn Tree $(m, 1, k)$ are Antimagic.

Proof:

Edges of Upper Layer; $e_{2j-1} = (u_{2j-1}, v_{2j})$: for $j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)

Edges of Lower Layer; $e_{2j} = (u_{2j}, v_{2j+1})$: for $j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)

Edges on Central Line are: $e_{m+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1})$: for $j = 1$ to m (left to right)

The Edge Labels are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(u_{2j-1}, v_{2j}) &= 2j - 1 : j = 1 \text{ to } m/2 && // \text{ left to right on Upper Layer } // \\
 f(u_{2j}, v_{2j+1}) &= 2j : j = 1 \text{ to } m/2 && // \text{ left to right on Lower Layer } // \\
 f(v_j, v_{j+1}) &= 2m - j + 1 : j = 1 \text{ to } m && // \text{ Central Line, left to right } //
 \end{aligned}$$

The induced Vertex Labels are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^*(u_{2j-1}) &= 2j - 1 && // \text{ Pendant vertices of Upper Layer } // \\
 f^*(u_{2j}) &= 2j && // \text{ Pendant vertices of Lower Layer } //
 \end{aligned}$$

// Pendant vertices make an arithmetic progression with common difference 2 //

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^*(v_1) &= 2m \text{ or } p && // \text{ leftmost vertex on Central Line } // \\
 f^*(v_j) &= 4m - j + 2 ; j = 2 \text{ to } m && // \text{ intermediate vertices on Central Line } // \\
 f^*(v_{n+1}) &= 2m + 1 \text{ or } p + 1 && // \text{ right most vertex on Central Line } //
 \end{aligned}$$

// Central line vertices make an arithmetic progression with common difference -1 except leftmost and rightmost vertices //

Since all the induced vertex labels are distinct therefore, the Thorn Tree $(m, 1, k)$ are Antimagic.

Results:

Upper and Lower Layer(s) vertex are labelled with common difference 2, Central line vertex are labelled with common difference -1 except Left and Right most vertex, Left most vertex of central line is labelled with p or $2m$, Right most vertex of Central Line is labelled with $p + 1$ or $2m + 1$.

Figure 4: Thorn Tree $(8, 1, 9)$ or Tree $(T(17, 16))$; 17 vertices, 16 edges

Illustration: *Thorn Tree* (8,1,9) $\Rightarrow T(17, 16)$, // $m = 8$, $k = 9$, $p = 16$ //

For $j = 1$ to $m/2$ i.e., for $j = 1$ to 4

Upper Layer edges $e_{2j-1} = (u_{2j-1}, v_{2j})$ labeled with $2j - 1$ i.e., 1, 3, 5, 7 // left to right //

Lower Layer edges $e_{2j} = (u_{2j}, v_{2j+1})$ labeled with $2j$ i.e., 2, 4, 6, 8 // left to right //

Central Line edges $e_{2n+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1})$ labeled with $(p$ to $p - m + 1) : p = 16$ to $p - m + 1 = 9$, or $2m - j + 1; j = 1$ to m i.e., 16, 15, 14, 13, 12, 11, 10, 9 // left to right //

Induced vertex labels:

Upper Layer pendant vertices u_{2j-1} with $2j - 1$ i.e., 1, 3, 5, 7 // left to right //

Lower Layer pendant vertices u_{2j} with $2j$ i.e., 2, 4, 6, 8 // left to right //

Central Line: leftmost vertex v_1 : $2m = 16$, intermediate 7 vertices v_j for $j = 2$ to 8 i.e. $v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7, v_8$: $4m - j + 2 = 32, 31, 30, \dots, 26$; rightmost vertex $v_9: p+1=17$.

Vertices:

Pendant vertices of Upper Layer (UL_1); $u_{2j-1} : j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)

Pendant vertices of Lower Layer (LL_1); $u_{2j} : j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)

Intermediate vertices of UL_i & UL_{i+1} ; $u_{mi+2j-1} : i = 1$ to $n - 1 ; j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)

Intermediate vertices of LL_i & LL_{i+1} ; $u_{mi+2j} : i = 1$ to $n - 1 ; j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)

Vertices on the Central Line; $v_j : j = 1$ to $m + 1$ (left to right)

Edges:

Edges of UL_i ; $e_{m(i-1)+2j-1} = (u_{m(i-1)+2j-1}, u_{mi+2j-1}) : i = 1$ to $n - 1 ; j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)

Edges of LL_i ; $e_{m(i-1)+2j} = (u_{m(i-1)+2j}, u_{mi+2j}) : i = 1$ to $n - 1 ; j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)

Edges of UL_n just above the central line; $e_{m(n-1)+2j-1} = (u_{m(n-1)+2j-1}, v_{2j}) : j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)

Edges of LL_n just below the central line; $e_{m(n-1)+2j} = (u_{m(n-1)+2j}, v_{2j+1}) : j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)

Edges on Central Line are: $e_{mn+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1}) : j = 1$ to m (left to right)

Figure 5: Thorn Tree (4, 2, 5) or Tree ($T(13, 12)$); 13 vertices, 12 edges)

Illustration: $Thorn\ Tree\ (4, 2, 5) \Rightarrow T(13, 12)$, // $m = 4, n = 2, k = 5, p = 12$ //
For $j = 1$ to $m/2$ i.e., for $j = 1$ to 2

Pendant edges of Upper Layer (UL_1); $e_{2j-1} = (u_{2j-1}, u_{2j+3})$ labeled with $2j - 1$ i.e.,
1, 3 // left to right //

Pendant edges of Lower Layer (LL_1); $e_{2j} = (u_{2j}, u_{2j+4})$ labeled with $2j$ i.e., 2, 4
// left to right //

Edges of Upper Layer (UL_2) just above the central line; $e_{2j+3} = (u_{2j+3}, v_{2j})$ labeled with
 $2j + 3$ i.e., 5, 7 // left to right //

Edges of Lower Layer (LL_2) just below the central line; $e_{2j+4} = (u_{2j+4}, v_{2j+1})$ labeled with
 $2j + 4$ i.e., 6, 8 // left to right //

For $j = 1$ to m i.e., for $j = 1$ to 4

Central Line edges $e_{2m+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1})$ labeled with $2m + j$: i.e., 9, 10, 11, 12
// left to right //

Induced vertex labels:

Pendant vertices of Upper Layer (UL_1) u_{2j-1} with $2j - 1$ i.e., 1, 3 // left to right //

Pendant vertices of Lower Layer (LL_1) u_{2j} with $2j$ i.e., 2, 4 // left to right //

Intermediate vertices of UL_1 & UL_2 ; u_{2j+3} with $4j + 2$ i.e., 6, 10 // left to right //

Intermediate vertices of LL_1 & LL_2 ; u_{2j+4} with $4(j + 1)$ i.e., 8, 12 // left to right //

Central Line: leftmost vertex v_1 : $2m + 1 = 9$, intermediate 3 vertices v_j for $j = 2$ to 4 i.e.
 v_2, v_3, v_4 : $3j + 18 = 24, 27, 30$; rightmost vertex v_5 : $5m = 20$.

Algorithm for Thorn (m, n, k):

```

//  $p + 1$  vertices,  $p$  edges;  $p = m(n + 1), k = m + 1$  //
Begin
for  $i = 1$  to  $n - 1$ 
    for  $j = 1$  to  $m/2$ 
        Label the edges of  $UL_i$  with  $m(i - 1) + 2j - 1$  from left to right
        // There are  $n$  edge in each Layer //
    end for  $j$ 
end for  $i$ 
for  $i = 1$  to  $n - 1$ 
    for  $j = 1$  to  $m/2$ 
        Label the edges of  $LL_i$  with  $m(i - 1) + 2j$  from left to right
    end for  $j$ 
end for  $i$ 
for  $j = 1$  to  $m/2$ 
    Label the edges of  $UL_n$  just above the central line with  $m(n - 1) + 2j - 1$  from left
    to right
end for
for  $j = 1$  to  $m/2$ 
    Label the edges of  $LL_n$  just above the central line with  $m(n - 1) + 2j$  from left to
    right
end for
for  $j = 1$  to  $m$ 
    Label Central Line edges with  $2m + j$  from left to right //  $m$  edges //
end for
End.

```

Theorem: Thorn Tree (m, n, k) are Antimagic.

Proof:

Edges of UL_i ; $e_{m(i-1)+2j-1} = (u_{m(i-1)+2j-1}, u_{mi+2j-1}) : i = 1$ to $n - 1 ; j = 1$ to $m/2$
 (left to right)

Edges of LL_i ; $e_{m(i-1)+2j} = (u_{m(i-1)+2j}, u_{mi+2j}) : i = 1$ to $n - 1 ; j = 1$ to $m/2$ (left to right)

Edges of UL_n just above the central line; $e_{m(n-1)+2j-1} = (u_{m(n-1)+2j-1}, v_{2j}) : j = 1$ to $m/2$
 (left to right)

Edges of LL_n just below the central line; $e_{m(n-1)+2j} = (u_{m(n-1)+2j}, v_{2j+1}) : j = 1$ to $m/2$
 (left to right)

Edges on Central Line are: $e_{mn+j} = (v_j, v_{j+1}) : j = 1$ to m (left to right)

The Edge Labels are as follows:

$$f(u_{m(i-1)+2j-1}, u_{mi+2j-1}) = m(i-1) + 2j - 1 : i = 1 \text{ to } n-1 ; j = 1 \text{ to } m/2$$

// left to right on UL_i //

$$f(u_{m(i-1)+2j}, u_{mi+2j}) = m(i-1) + 2j : i = 1 \text{ to } n-1 ; j = 1 \text{ to } m/2$$

// left to right on LL_i //

$$f(u_{m(n-1)+2j-1}, v_{2j}) = m(n-1) + 2j - 1 : j = 1 \text{ to } m/2 // \text{ left to right on } UL_n \text{ just above the central line } //$$

$$f(u_{m(n-1)+2j}, v_{2j+1}) = m(n-1) + 2j : j = 1 \text{ to } m/2 // \text{ left to right on } LL_n \text{ just below the central line } //$$

$$f(v_j, v_{j+1}) = mn + j : j = 1 \text{ to } m // \text{ Central Line, left to right } //$$

The induced Vertex Labels are as follows:

$$f^*(u_{2j-1}) = 2j - 1 : j = 1 \text{ to } m/2 // \text{ Pendant vertices of } UL_1 //$$

$$f^*(u_{2j}) = 2j : j = 1 \text{ to } m/2 // \text{ Pendant vertices of } LL_1 //$$

// Pendant vertices make an arithmetic progression with common difference 2 //

$$f^*(u_{mi+2j-1}) = (2i-1)m + 4j - 2 : i = 1 \text{ to } n-1 ; j = 1 \text{ to } m/2$$

// Intermediate vertices of UL_i & UL_{i+1} //

$$f^*(u_{mi+2j}) = (2i-1)m + 4j : i = 1 \text{ to } n-1 ; j = 1 \text{ to } m/2$$

// Intermediate vertices of LL_i & LL_{i+1} //

// Intermediate vertices make an arithmetic progression with common difference 4 //

$$f^*(v_1) = mn + 1 // \text{ leftmost vertex on Central Line } //$$

$$f^*(v_j) = m(3n-1) + 4 + 3(j-2) ; j = 2 \text{ to } m // \text{ intermediate vertices on Central Line } //$$

$$f^*(v_{n+1}) = m(2n+1) // \text{ right most vertex on Central Line } //$$

// Central line vertices make an arithmetic progression with common difference 3 except leftmost and rightmost vertices //

Since all the induced vertex labels are distinct therefore, the Thorn Tree (m, n, k) are Antimagic.

Results:

Pendant vertices of Upper and Lower Layer make an arithmetic progression with common difference 2, Intermediate vertices of Upper and Lower Layer(s) make an arithmetic progression with common difference 4, Central line vertex are labelled with common difference 3 except Left and Right most vertex, Left most vertex of central line is labelled with $mn + 1$, Right most vertex of central line is labelled with $m(2n + 1)$.

Figure 6: Thorn Tree (8, 4, 9) or Tree (T(41, 40); 41 vertices, 40 edges)

Illustration: Thorn Tree (8, 4, 9) $\Rightarrow$ T(41, 40), // $m = 8, n = 4, k = 9, p = 40$ //

For $j = 1$ to $m/2$ i.e., for $j = 1$ to 4

Upper Layer (UL_1) edges $e_{2j-1} = (u_{2j-1}, u_{m+2j-1})$ labeled with $2j - 1$ i.e., 1, 3, 5, 7 // left to right //

Lower Layer (LL_1) edges $e_{2j} = (u_{2j}, u_{m+2j})$ labeled with $2j$ i.e., 2, 4, 6, 8 // left to right //

Upper Layer (UL_2) edges $e_{2j+7} = (u_{2j+7}, u_{2j+15})$ labeled with $2j + 7$ i.e. 9, 11, 13, 15 // left to right //

Lower Layer (LL_2) edges $e_{2j+8} = (u_{2j+8}, u_{2j+16})$ labeled with $2j + 8$ i.e. 10, 12, 14, 16 // left to right //

Upper Layer (UL_3) edges $e_{2j+15} = (u_{2j+15}, u_{2j+23})$ labeled with $2j + 15$ i.e. 17, 19, 21, 23 // left to right //

Lower Layer (LL_3) edges $e_{2j+16} = (u_{2j+16}, u_{2j+24})$ labeled with $2j + 16$ i.e. 18, 20, 22, 24 // left to right //

Edges of UL_4 just above the central line; $e_{2j+23} = (u_{2j+23}, v_{2j})$ labeled with $2j + 23$ i.e., 25, 27, 29, 31 // left to right //

Edges of LL_4 just below the central line; $e_{2j+24} = (u_{2j+24}, v_{2j+1})$ labeled with $2j + 24$ i.e., 26, 28, 30, 32 // left to right //

For $j = 1$ to m i.e., for $j = 1$ to 8

Central Line edges $e_{j+32} = (v_j, v_{j+1})$ labeled with $j + 32$: i.e., 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40 // left to right //

Induced vertex labels:

Pendant vertices Upper Layer(s) u_{2j-1} with $2j-1$ i.e., 1, 3, 5, 7 // left to right //

Pendant vertices Lower Layer(s) u_{2j} with $2j$ i.e., 2, 4, 6, 8 // left to right //

Vertices of Intermediate layer of Upper Layer(s); $u_{mi+2j-1} : i = 1 \text{ to } n-1 ; j = 1 \text{ to } m/2$
i.e. $i = 1 \text{ to } 3$ with $(2i-1)m + 4j - 2$ // left to right // i.e.,

for $i = 1$; 10, 14, 18, 22

for $i = 2$; 26, 30, 34, 38

for $i = 3$; 42, 46, 50, 54

Vertices of Intermediate layer of Lower Layer(s); $u_{mi+2j} : i = 1 \text{ to } n-1 ; j = 1 \text{ to } m/2$
i.e. $i = 1 \text{ to } 3$ with $(2i-1)m + 4j$ // left to right // i.e.,

for $i = 1$; 12, 16, 20, 24

for $i = 2$; 28, 32, 36, 40

for $i = 3$; 44, 48, 52, 56

Central Line: leftmost vertex v_1 : $4m + 1 = 33$, intermediate 7 vertices v_j for $j = 2 \text{ to } 8$
i.e. $v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7, v_8$: $11m + 3j - 2 = 92, 95, 98, 101, 104, 107, 110$; rightmost
vertex v_5 : $9m = 72$.

2.3 Bush Trees:

Bush Tree $B(l, m, n)$: From a Central vertex C , l number of edges joined to m no. of edges which in turn are joined to n no. of pendant edges.

Antimagic labellings are obtained for the Bush Trees examined as follows:
 $B(4, 3, n)$, $n = 15$; $B(5, 2, n)$, $n = 15$; Repetition of exactly one vertex label obtained with rest of the vertex labels being distinct: $B(3, 2, n)$; $B(3, 3, n)$; $B(4, 2, n)$; $B(4, 4, n)$; the repeated vertex labels are mentioned in bold letters in the Tables.

Description and Naming of the Vertices and Edges for Bush Trees $B(l, m, n) \Rightarrow T(p+1, p)$ // $p+1$ vertices, p edges; $p = l + lm + lmn$ //

Vertices:

End-vertices of Pendant Layer edges (Upper and Lower) EVPLE; $u_i : i = 1 \text{ to } lmn$ starting from any Pendant vertex and continue towards right (Clockwise) of the u_1 .

End-vertices of Outer Layer edges (Upper and Lower) EVOLE; $v_j : j = 1 \text{ to } lm$, where v_1 is the inner vertex joined with u_1 to u_n , for the next bunch v_2 with u_{n+1} to u_{2n} , and similarly towards right (Clockwise) of the 1st bunch.

End-vertices of Inner Layer edges (Upper and Lower) EVILE; $w_k: k=1$ to l , where w_1 is the joined with v_1 to v_m , for the next similarly towards right (Clockwise) of the w_1 .

Central vertex C:

Edges:

Edges of Pendant Layer (Upper and Lower): $e_{n(j-1)+i} = v_j u_{n(j-1)+i}$; for $j=1$ to lm and $i=1$ to n

Edges of Outer Layer (Upper and Lower): $e_{lmn+(k-1)m+j} = w_k v_{(k-1)m+j}$; for $k=1$ to l and $j=1$ to m

Edges of Inner Layer (Upper and Lower): $e_{lm(n+1)+k} = cw_k$; for $k=1$ to l

Figure 7: Bush Tree (4, 3, 3)

Algorithm for Bush Tree (l, m, n):

```

// p + 1 vertices, p edges; p = l + lm + lmn //
Begin
for i = 1 to lmn
    Label the Pendant edges (Upper and Lower Layer) with i start from e1 continue
    towards right (Clockwise) of the e1
    // There are lmn Pendant edges //
end i

```

for $j = 1$ to lm
 Label the edges of Outer Layer (Upper and Lower) with $lmn + j$ start from e_{lmn+1}
 continue towards right (Clockwise) of the e_{lmn+1}
 // There are lm edges of Outer Layer //
 end j
 for $k = 1$ to l
 Label the edges of Inner Layer (Upper and Lower) with $lm(n + 1) + k$ start from
 $e_{lm(n+1)+1}$ continue towards right (Clockwise) of the $e_{lm(n+1)+1}$
 // There are l edges of Inner Layer //
 end k
 End.

Theorem: *Bush Tree $B(l, m, n)$ are Antimagic.*

Proof:

Edges of Pendant Layer (Upper and Lower): $e_{n(j-1)+i} = v_j u_{n(j-1)+i}$; for $j = 1$ to lm and
 $i = 1$ to n

Edges of Outer Layer (Upper and Lower): $e_{lmn+(k-1)m+j} = w_k v_{(k-1)m+j}$; for $k = 1$ to l
 and $j = 1$ to m

Edges of Inner Layer (Upper and Lower): $e_{lm(n+1)+k} = c w_k$; for $k = 1$ to l

The Edge Labels are as follows:

$$f(v_j, u_{n(j-1)+i}) = n(j-1) + i; \text{ for } j = 1 \text{ to } lm \text{ and } i = 1 \text{ to } n \quad (1)$$

// from 1 to lmn , continue towards right (Clockwise) of the e_1 //

$$f(w_k, v_{(k-1)m+j}) = lmn + (k-1)m + j; \text{ for } k = 1 \text{ to } l \text{ and } j = 1 \text{ to } m \quad (2)$$

// from $(lmn + 1)$ to $lm(n + 1)$, continue towards right (Clockwise) of the
 e_{lmn+1} //

$$f(c, w_k) = lm(n + 1) + k; \text{ for } k = 1 \text{ to } l \quad (3)$$

// from $(lm(n + 1) + 1)$ to $l(m(n + 1) + 1)$, continue towards right
 (Clockwise) of the $e_{lm(n+1)+1}$ //

The induced Vertex Labels are as follows:

$$f^*(u_i) = i; \text{ for } i = 1 \text{ to } lmn \quad (4)$$

// End- vertices of Pendant Layer edges (Upper and Lower) EVPLE are consecutive integers//

$$f^*(v_j) = (lmn + 1) + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} + (j-1)d, \quad d = n^2 + 1; \text{ for } j = 1 \text{ to } lm \quad (5)$$

// End- vertices of Outer Layer edges (Upper and Lower) EVOLE make an *arithmetic progression* with common difference $n^2 + 1$ //

$$f^*(w_k) = lmn(m + 1) + (lm + 1) + \frac{m(m+1)}{2} + (k - 1)d, d = m^2 + 1; \\ k=1 \text{ to } l \tag{6}$$

// End- vertices of Inner Layer edges (Upper and Lower) EVOLE make an *arithmetic progression* with common difference $m^2 + 1$ //

$$f^*(c) = l^2m(n + 1) + \frac{l(l+1)}{2} \quad // \text{ Central vertex } // \tag{7}$$

Since all the induced vertex labels are distinct. Therefore, the *Bush Tree* $B(l, m, n)$ are *Antimagic*.

Results:

Pendent vertex of Upper and Lower layer are labelled with common difference 1 i.e., consecutive integers. End- vertices of Outer Layer edges (Upper and Lower) are labelled with common difference $n^2 + 1$ start from $(lmn + 1) + \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$, end- vertices of Inner Layer edges (Upper and Lower) are labelled with common difference $m^2 + 1$ starting from $lmn(m + 1) + (lm + 1) + \frac{m(m+1)}{2}$ and difference between Initial end-vertex label of Inner Layer edges is $lm(m + 1)$, Central vertex is labelled with $l^2m(n + 1) + \frac{l(l+1)}{2}$, the difference between the Central vertex label of the next Bush Tree and that of the previous Bush Tree is constant with the difference being $= l^2m$.

Table for Bush Tree (4, 3, n):

- EVPLE: End-Vertex of Pendant Layer Edges: 1 to $12n$
- IEVOLE: Initial End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges: $(12n+1) + \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$, $d = n^2 + 1$
- IEVILE: Initial End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges: $48n + 19, d = 10$
- C: Central Vertex: $48n + 58$

Bush Tree (4, 3, n)	EVOLE(End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges)	d	EVILE(End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges)	C(Central Vertex)
(4,3,2)	28, 33, 38, 43, 48, 53, 58, 63, 68, 73, 78, 83	5	115, 125, 135, 145	154
(4,3,3)	43, 53, 63, 73, 83, 93, 103, 113, 123, 133, 143, 153	10	163, 173, 183, 193	202
(4,3,4)	59, 76, 93, 110, 127, 144, 161, 178, 195, 212, 229, 246	17	211, 221, 231, 241	250
(4,3,5)	76, 102, 128, 154, 180, 206, 232, 258, 284, 310, 336, 362	26	259, 269, 279, 289	298
(4,3,6)	94, 131, 168, 205, 242, 279, 316, 353, 390, 427, 464, 501	37	307, 317, 327, 337	346
(4,3,7)	113, 163, 213, 263, 313, 363, 413, 463, 513, 563, 613, 663	50	355, 365, 375, 385	394
(4,3,8)	133, 198, 263, 328, 393, 458, 523, 588, 653, 718, 783, 848	65	403, 413, 423, 433	442
(4,3,9)	154, 236, 318, 400, 482, 564, 646, 728, 810, 892, 974, 1056	82	451, 461, 471, 481	490
(4,3,10)	176, 277, 378, 479, 580, 681, 782, 883, 984, 1085, 1186, 1287	101	499, 509, 519, 529	538
(4,3,11)	199, 321, 443, 565, 687, 809, 931, 1053, 1175, 1297, 1419, 1541	122	547, 557, 567, 577	586
(4,3,12)	223, 368, 513, 658, 803, 948, 1093, 1238, 1383, 1528, 1673, 1818	145	595, 605, 615, 625	634
(4,3,13)	248, 418, 588, 758, 928, 1098, 1268, 1438, 1608, 1778	170	643, 653, 663, 673	682
(4,3,14)	274, 471, 668, 865, 1062, 1259, 1456, 1653, 1850, 2047, 2244, 2441	197	691, 701, 711, 721	730
(4,3,15)	301, 527, 753, 979, 1205, 1431, 1657, 1883, 2109, 2335, 2561, 2787	226	739, 749, 759, 769	778

Figure 8: Bush Tree (5, 2, 4)

Table for Bush Tree (5, 2, n):

End-Vertex of Pendant Layer Edges (EVPLE): 1 to $10n$

Initial End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges (IEVOLE): $(10n+1) + \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$,
 $d = n^2 + 1$

Initial End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges (IEVILE): $30n + 14$, $d=5$

Central Vertex (C): $50n + 65$

Bush Tree (5, 2, n)	EVOLE(End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges)	d	EVILE(End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges)	C(Central Vertex)
(5,2,2)	24, 29, 34, 39, 44, 49, 54, 59, 64, 69	5	74, 79, 84, 89, 94	165
(5,2,3)	37, 47, 57, 67, 77, 87, 97, 107, 117, 127	10	104, 109, 114, 119, 124	215
(5,2,4)	51, 68, 85, 102, 119, 136, 153, 170, 187, 204	17	134, 139, 144, 149, 154	265
(5,2,5)	66, 92, 118, 144, 170, 196, 222, 248, 274, 300	26	164, 169, 174, 179, 184	315

(5,2,6)	82, 119, 156, 193, 230, 267, 304, 341, 378, 415	37	194, 199, 204, 209, 214	365
(5,2,7)	99, 149, 199, 249, 299, 349, 399, 449, 499, 549	50	224, 229, 234, 239, 244	415
(5,2,8)	117, 182, 247, 312, 377, 442, 507, 572, 637, 702	65	254, 259, 264, 269, 274	465
(5,2,9)	136, 218, 300, 382, 464, 546, 628, 710, 792, 874	82	284, 289, 294, 299, 304	515
(5,2,10)	156, 257, 358, 459, 560, 661, 762, 863, 964, 1065	101	314, 319, 324, 329, 334	565
(5,2,11)	177, 299, 421, 543, 665, 787, 909, 1031, 1153, 1275	122	344, 349, 354, 359, 364	615
(5,2,12)	199, 344, 489, 634, 779, 924, 1069, 1214, 1359, 1504	145	374, 379, 384, 389, 394	665
(5,2,13)	222, 392, 562, 732, 902, 1072, 1242, 1412, 1582, 1752	170	404, 409, 414, 419, 424	715
(5,2,14)	246, 443, 640, 837, 1034, 1231, 1428, 1625, 1822, 2019	197	434, 439, 444, 449, 454	765
(5,2,15)	271, 497, 723, 949, 1175, 1401, 1627, 1853, 2079, 2305	226	474, 479, 484, 489, 494	815

Table for Bush Tree (5, 3, n):

EVPLE: End-Vertex of Pendant Layer Edges: 1 to $15n$

IEVOLE: Initial End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges: $(15n+1) + \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$,
 $d = n^2 + 1$

IEVILE: Initial End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges: $60n + 22$, $d = 10$

C: Central Vertex: $75n + 90$

Bush Tree (5, 3, n)	EVOLE (End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges)	d	EVILE (End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges)	C (Central Vertex)
(5,3,2)	34, 39, 44, 49, 54, 59, 64, 69, 74, 79, 84, 89, 94, 99, 104	5	142, 152, 162, 172, 182	240
(5,3,3)	52, 62, 72, 82, 92, 102, 112, 122, 132, 142, 152, 162, 172, 182, 192	10	202, 212, 222, 232, 242	315
(5,3,4)	71, 88, 105, 122, 139, 156, 173, 190, 207, 224, 241, 258, 275, 292 , 309	17	262, 272, 282, 292 (Repeat), 302	390
(5,3,5)	91, 117, 143, 169, 195, 221, 247, 273, 299, 325, 351, 377, 403, 429, 455	26	322, 332, 342, 352, 362	465
(5,3,6)	112, 149, 186, 223, 260, 297, 334, 371, 408, 445, 482, 519, 556, 593, 630	37	382, 392, 402, 412, 422	540
(5,3,7)	134, 184, 234, 284, 334, 384, 434, 484, 534, 584, 634, 684, 734, 784, 834	50	442, 452, 462, 472, 482	615
(5,3,8)	157, 222, 287, 352, 417, 482, 547, 612, 677, 742, 807, 872, 937, 1002, 1067	65	502, 512, 522, 532, 542	690
(5,3,9)	181, 263, 345, 427, 509, 591, 673, 755, 837, 919, 1001, 1083, 1165, 1247, 1329	82	562, 572, 582, 592, 602	765
(5,3,10)	206, 307, 408, 509, 610, 711, 812, 913, 1014, 1115, 1216, 1317, 1418, 1519, 1620	101	622, 632, 642, 652, 662	840
(5,3,11)	232, 354, 476, 598, 720, 842, 964, 1086, 1208, 1330, 1452, 1574, 1696, 1818, 1940	122	682, 692, 702, 712, 722	915
(5,3,12)	259, 404, 549, 694, 839, 984, 1129, 1274, 1419, 1564, 1709, 1854, 1999, 2144, 2289	145	742, 752, 762, 772, 782	990
(5,3,13)	287, 457, 627, 797, 967, 1137, 1307, 1477, 1647, 1817, 1987, 2157, 2327, 2497, 2667	170	802, 812, 822, 832, 842	1065
(5,3,14)	316, 513, 710, 907, 1104, 1301, 1498, 1695, 1892, 2089, 2286, 2483, 2680, 2877, 3074	197	862, 872, 882, 892, 902	1140
(5,3,15)	346, 572, 798, 1024, 1250, 1476, 1702, 1928, 2154, 2380, 2606, 2832, 3058, 3284, 3510	226	922, 932, 942, 952, 962	1215

Figure 9: Bush Tree (3, 2, 6)

Table for Bush Tree (3, 2, n):

End-Vertex of Pendant Layer Edges (EVPLE): 1 to $6n$

Initial End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges (IEVOLE): $(6n+1) + \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$,
 $d = n^2 + 1$

Initial End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges (IEVILE): $18n + 10$, $d = 5$

Central Vertex (C): $18n + 24$

Bush Tree (3, 2, n)	EVOLE(End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges)	d	EVILE(End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges)	C(Central Vertex)
(3,2,2)	16, 21, 26, 31, 36, 41	5	46, 51, 56	60
(3,2,3)	25, 35, 45, 55, 65, 75	10	64, 69, 74	78
(3,2,4)	35, 52, 69, 86, 103, 120	17	82, 87, 92	96
(3,2,5)	46, 72, 98, 124, 150, 176	26	100, 105, 110	114
(3,2,6)	58, 95, 132 , 169, 206, 243	37	118, 123, 128	132(Repeat)

(3,2,7)	71, 121, 171, 221, 271, 321	50	136, 141, 146	150
(3,2,8)	85, 150, 215, 280, 345, 410	65	154, 159, 164	168
(3,2,9)	100, 182 , 264, 346, 428, 510	82	172, 177, 182(Repeat)	186
(3,2,10)	116, 217, 318, 419, 520, 621	101	190, 195, 200	204
(3,2,11)	133, 255, 377, 499, 621, 743	122	208, 213, 218	222
(3,2,12)	151, 296, 441, 586, 731, 876	145	226, 231, 236	240
(3,2,13)	170, 340, 510, 680, 850, 1020	170	244, 249, 254	258
(3,2,14)	190, 387, 584, 781, 978, 1175	197	262, 267, 272	276
(3,2,15)	211, 437, 663, 889, 1115, 1341	226	280, 285, 290	294

Table for Bush Tree (3, 3, n):

EVPLE: End-Vertex of Pendant Layer Edges: 1 to $9n$

IEVOLE: Initial End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges: $(9n+1) + \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$,
 $d = n^2 + 1$

IEVILE: Initial End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges: $36n + 16$, $d = 10$

C: Central Vertex: $27n + 33$

Bush Tree (3, 3, n)	EVOLE (End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges)	d	EVILE (End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges)	C (Central Vertex)
(3,3,2)	22, 27, 32, 37, 42, 47, 52, 57, 62	5	88, 98, 108	87
(3,3,3)	34, 44, 54, 64, 74, 84, 94, 104, 114	10	124, 134, 144	114(Repeat)
(3,3,4)	47, 64, 81, 98, 115, 132, 149, 166, 183	17	160, 170, 180	141
(3,3,5)	61, 87, 113, 139, 165, 191, 217, 243, 269	26	196, 206, 216	168
(3,3,6)	76, 113, 150, 187, 224, 261, 298, 335, 372	37	232, 242, 252	195
(3,3,7)	92, 142, 192, 242, 292, 342, 392, 442, 492	50	268, 278, 288	222

(3,3,8)	109, 174, 239, 304, 369, 434, 499, 564, 629	65	304(Repeat), 314, 324	249
(3,3,9)	127, 209, 291, 373, 455, 537, 619, 701, 783	82	340, 350, 360	276
(3,3,10)	146, 247, 348, 449, 550, 651, 752, 853, 954	101	376, 386, 396	303
(3,3,11)	166, 288, 410, 532, 654, 776, 898, 1020, 1142	122	412, 422, 432	330
(3,3,12)	187, 326, 471, 616, 761, 906, 1051, 1196, 1341	145	448, 458, 468	357
(3,3,13)	209, 379, 549, 719, 889, 1059, 1229, 1399, 1569	170	484, 494, 504	384
(3,3,14)	232, 429, 626, 823, 1020, 1217, 1414, 1611, 1808	197	520, 530, 540	411
(3,3,15)	256, 482, 708, 934, 1160, 1386, 1612, 1838, 2064	226	556, 566, 576	438

Figure 10: Bush Tree (4, 2, 3)

Table for Bush Tree (4, 2, n):

End-Vertex of Pendant Layer Edges (EVPLE): 1 to $8n$, d is the common difference

Initial End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges (IEVOLE): $(8n+1) + \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$,
 $d = n^2 + 1$

Initial End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges (IEVILE): $24n + 12$, $d = 5$

Central Vertex (C): $32n + 42$

Bush Tree (4, 2, n)	EVOLE(End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges)	d	EVILE(End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges)	C(Central Vertex)
(4,2,2)	20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55	5	60, 65, 70, 75	106
(4,2,3)	31, 41, 51, 61, 71, 81, 91, 101	10	84, 89, 94, 99	138
(4,2,4)	43, 60, 77, 94, 111, 128, 145, 162	17	108, 113, 118, 123	170
(4,2,5)	56, 82, 108, 134, 160, 186, 212, 238	26	132, 137, 142, 147	202
(4,2,6)	70, 107, 144, 181, 218, 255, 292, 329	37	156, 161, 166, 171	234
(4,2,7)	85, 135, 185 , 235, 285, 335, 385, 435	50	180, 185(Repeat) , 190, 195	266
(4,2,8)	101, 166, 231, 296, 361, 426, 491, 556	65	204, 209, 214, 219	298
(4,2,9)	118, 200, 282, 364, 446, 528, 610, 692	82	228, 233, 238, 243	330
(4,2,10)	136, 237, 338, 439, 540, 641, 742, 843	101	252, 257, 262, 267	362
(4,2,11)	155, 277, 399, 521, 643, 765, 887, 1009	122	276, 281, 286, 291	394
(4,2,12)	175, 320, 465, 610, 755, 900, 1045, 1190	145	300, 305, 310, 315	426
(4,2,13)	196, 366, 536, 706, 876, 1046, 1216, 1386	170	324, 329, 334, 339	458
(4,2,14)	218, 415, 612, 809, 1006, 1203, 1400, 1597	197	348, 353, 358, 363	490
(4,2,15)	241, 467, 693, 919, 1145, 1371, 1597, 1823	226	372, 377, 382, 387	522

Table for Bush Tree (4, 4, n):

EVPLE: End-Vertex of Pendant Layer Edges: 1 to $16n$

IEVOLE: Initial End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges: $(16n+1) + \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$,
 $d = n^2 + 1$

IEVILE: Initial End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges: $80n + 27$, $d = 17$

C: Central Vertex: $64n + 74$

Bush Tree (4, 4, n)	EVOLE(End-Vertex of Outer Layer Edges)	d	EVILE(End-Vertex of Inner Layer Edges)	C(Central Vertex)
(4,4,2)	36, 41, 46, 51, 56, 61, 66, 71, 76, 81, 86, 91, 96, 101, 106, 111	5	187, 204, 221, 238	202
(4,4,3)	55, 65, 75, 85, 95, 105, 115, 125, 135, 145, 155, 165, 175, 185, 195, 205	10	267, 284, 301, 318	266
(4,4,4)	75, 92, 109, 126, 143, 160, 177, 194, 211, 228, 245, 262, 279, 296, 313, 330	17	347, 364, 381, 398	330(Repeat)
(4,4,5)	96, 122, 148, 174, 200, 226, 252, 278, 304, 330, 356, 382, 408, 434, 460, 486	26	427, 444, 461, 478	394
(4,4,6)	118, 155, 192, 229, 266, 303, 340, 377, 414, 451, 488, 525, 562, 599, 636, 673	37	507, 524, 541, 558	458
(4,4,7)	141, 191, 241, 291, 341, 391, 441, 491, 541, 591, 641, 691, 741, 791, 841, 891	50	587, 604, 621, 638	522
(4,4,8)	165, 230, 295, 360, 425, 490, 555, 620, 685, 750, 815, 880, 945, 1010, 1075, 1140	65	667, 684, 701, 718	586
(4,4,9)	190, 272, 354, 436, 518, 600, 682, 764, 846, 928, 1010, 1092, 1174, 1256, 1338, 1420	82	747, 764, 781, 798	650
(4,4,10)	216, 317, 418, 519, 620, 721, 822, 923, 1024, 1125, 1226, 1327, 1428, 1529, 1630, 1731	101	827, 844, 861, 878	714
(4,4,11)	243, 365, 487, 609, 731, 853, 975, 1097, 1219, 1341, 1463, 1585, 1707, 1829, 1951, 2073	122	907, 924, 941, 958	778
(4,4,12)	271, 441, 611, 781, 951, 1121, 1291, 1461, 1631, 1801, 1971, 2141, 2311, 2481, 2651, 2821	170	987, 1004, 1021, 1038	842

3. Conclusion:

Three new classes of Trees-Arrow, Thorn and Bush Trees exhibiting Antimagic labellings have been presented in this work along with their algorithms, theorems and formulas. These Trees by virtue of their unique structures could find various applications in future developments.

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